

THE USE OF STYLISTIC FEATURES IN COMPLEX SENTENCES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF T. JUMAMURATOV'S WORKS)

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Annotation.

This article discusses the features of the use of joint sentences in T. Jumamuratov's works.

Key words: language, joint sentence, poetry style, syntactic repetition, inversion, parallelism, ellipsis, antithesis.

World literature includes various forms of artistic works created by different peoples. The originality of a writer or poet's style is revealed through stylistic figures. Both prose and poetry works are distinguished by their emotionality and expressiveness. This feature is especially noticeable in poetic language. The harmony of lines, rhythm, and richness of thought ensure the emotional impact of art. Stylistic figures are expressive tools such as inversion, tautology, parallelism, antithesis, gradation, ellipsis, rhetorical question. Their frequent use in poetic works demonstrates the uniqueness of the writer's or poet's style. Complex sentences give poetry depth, while poetic effectiveness is ensured through syntactic connection of clauses.

The language of poetry, with its syntactic features, is particularly enriched by the use of complex sentences. In modern Karakalpak literature, the use of complex sentences is clearly noticeable. In Russian linguistics, N. S. Pospelov pointed out the syntactic features of complex constructions in Pushkin's works [1]. In Kazakh linguistics, R. Sızdyqova studied the syntactic features of Abai's poetic language [2]. Thus, researchers emphasized that syntactic peculiarities of complex constructions play a significant role in poetic speech.

Compared to prose, in poetry the arrangement of syntactic elements, rhythm, and logical flow are especially important. When we look at written prose sentences, complex sentences are mainly connected through syntactic coordination, whereas in poetry they are characterized by stylistic repetitions and logical consistency. In Russian linguistics, N. S. Pospelov identified the following features of complex constructions: 1) close connection of words within complex sentences; 2) when connecting one clause to another, weak syntactic dependence is replaced by vertical coordination; 3) various means are used to connect subordinate clauses, often through auxiliary words; 4) use of inversion when arranging words within the clauses; 5) syntactic service of repetitions

within clauses; 6) division of complex sentences into segments, with each segment maintaining its structural independence.

In poetic language, thoughts are combined into a single whole. Each sentence is connected with the next, usually forming a chain of complex sentences. Such constructions help better reveal the idea of the work. Parallelisms are frequently used. Complex sentences are not just built as a chain but also in a way that each clause retains its independence, while stylistically enhancing the poetic effect.

Parallelism.

Complex sentences are often built not just from two clauses but sometimes from three or more clauses connected together. In such cases, the idea is fully expressed by linking several clauses. Parallel syntactic constructions are arranged side by side. "Comparative parallelism" means placing sentences or constructions side by side in a syntactic structure. Parallelism is mostly found in poetic works. [4,84]

Parallelism is one of the main poetic (stylistic) devices, where the same thought is expressed by repeating it in a certain order. Poetic parallelism concretizes, strengthens, and highlights the image. Parallelism is used both in prose and poetry, but its effectiveness is more noticeable in poetic works. The semantic integrity of parallelism ensures that the internal connection of clauses in a compound sentence is maintained. Syntactic parallelism determines the rhythm of poetic lines, creating a sense of harmony. Events or situations coming in sequence can be compared with one another or contrasted. For example:

**"If there is water, there is heat,
If there is cold, there is suffering."**

In such compound sentences, each component has equal weight, and syntactic parallelism can express continuity, contrast, or comparison of events. Examples:

1. Contrast:

"If you say a wise one, I am here,
If you say a fool, I am here too,
If you say smart, I am here,
If you say fool, I am still here." ("Tortlikler")

2. Comparative relation:

"One thinks there is a jewel in his mind,
Another thinks there is steel in his strength."
("The Bright Dawn of This World")

Such examples can be found abundantly in the poet's works.

Repetition.

Repetition enhances meaning, intensity, and emotional effect. It makes the thought more expressive and can be used in various forms. Repetition is often found in compound sentences.

1. Successive repetition:

"Cotton — honor, cotton — fame, cotton — ...,
Cotton is the fruitful table." ("Uzbek Cotton")

2. In multi-component compound sentences, the sentence parts are often repeated.

This is also realized through epiphoric repetition.

For example:

"In every place there is cotton,
In every place there is a girl,
In every place there is a boy,
In every place there is a river,
In every place there is a people."

Such repetitions reinforce meaning, increase intensity, and heighten emotional impact.

Example:

"Live, life, live, O youth,
Pass eighty, pass ninety, reach a hundred." ("Törtlikler")
Ellipsis.

Ellipsis (omission of words) is a stylistic device where certain words are left out but understood in context. Elliptical sentences are common not only in simple clauses but also in compound ones. Omission gives brevity, conciseness, and expressiveness to poetic style.

Example:

"The beauty of the lake with reeds,
The beauty of the man with his hand." ("From my lyrical poems")
Exclamation (emphasis).

Another feature of compound sentence structure is the use of emphatic constructions. From the syntactic perspective, exclamation is a frequent tool of poetic speech, often found in compound sentences.

Antithesis.

In our language, one of the stylistic devices used to make thought sharper and more effective is antithesis. Antithesis is the use of opposing concepts within a single phrase to increase the sharpness of expression. Thus, the main function of antithesis is opposition. Antithesis occurs in all areas of language, but in compound sentences it plays a special role, serving not only to strengthen the idea but also to enhance expressiveness. Through placing contrasting concepts side by side and comparing them, antithesis is created.

In compound sentences, opposing meanings are expressed through the use of antonyms in both components. Example:

“When the good are honored in this world,
The evil are punished in the next world.” (“Tortlikler”)
“May you be joyful, may you be sorrowful,
May you be king, may you be poor,
May you die and become dust.” (“Tortlikler”)

Inversion (Latin *inversio* – rearrangement) is the change in the usual word order of sentence elements, used to give the sentence special artistic value (expressiveness). In compound sentences, the word order of clauses may also change, resulting in inversion. Example:

“Though the wild sea rages and foams,
They treat it as nothing, like a fish.” (“Törtlikler”)

In Turkic languages, including Karakalpak, there is a fixed order in the relationship between the subordinate and the main clause within subordinate compound sentences. According to this order, the subordinate clause usually precedes the main clause. However, in poetic works, due to stylistic requirements, the main clause may come first, followed by the subordinate clause.

In poetry, inversion may also occur because of rhyme patterns or for certain logical purposes in presenting the idea. Example:

“Beware of the reckless, if you are brave,
If you lean on a fool, your honor will fall.” (“Törtlikler”)

In artistic works, compound sentences are used very frequently to express thoughts concisely and clearly. The rhyme, rhythm, and equal syllable count in compound-sentence-based poetic lines ensure the emotionality and expressiveness of the idea.

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